
Research Article**School Budgeting, Accounting and Auditing in Nigeria**

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Abstract

This paper is on budgeting, accounting, and auditing as veritable tools school effectiveness school budget is defined here as a statement of the total educational programme for a given units, as well as an estimate of resources necessary to carry out the programme and the revenue needed to cover those expenditures. The following types of school budgets are discussed: line item, zero-caseo, and PPBS. The school budgeting, accounting and auditing attempt to determine the effective and efficient uses of resources and to provide the roadmap by which the stakeholders in education can evaluate school financial status to support the operation and improvement of education among other control techniques.

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Introduction

There are three major financial functions in education- budgeting, accounting, and auditing. There are separate, discrete, operations, but they are nonetheless closely interrelated. They require guidance, and accountability in the use-of-the-fund raised and expended in the year on school programme.

School as formal organization uses budget to facilitate annual decision making on expenditures, which provide for systematic presentation of recommendations of expenditures by the management to the governing council (Board of 'Governors). Budget provides a basis for ensuring that actual expenditures conform to needs of the schools. A budget may therefore be described as a financial plan that serves as the basic for

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expenditure, decision-making and subsequent control of expenditure. Budgeting is a control technique in the school system; hence it becomes an economic blueprint that reflects the amount of resources available (Ajia, 2002).

Budget also means an expression of purpose and educational programme, it is the reflection of past performance including both successes and failures. It is also a reflection of hope for those optimistic features when success will predominate and failure minimized (Nwankwo, 1980). Budget is used in the school system as disciplinary agents to control the use of resources devoted to particular purpose.

School Budgeting

School Budget like other budgets usually contains, financial data for the previous year (s), estimated figure for the current year, and recommended figure for the coming year, for- both expenditures and revenues. Most of the spaces in the budget however, are devoted to expenditures. Budgeting is the process, and plan for determining how money is to be raised and spent, as to document the budget- developed and approved during the budgeting process.

William (1999) defines educational budget as a "working tool" for the successful operation of schools and as a "significant opportunity to plan the mission, achieve their education objectives.

In more technical terms, school total educational programme for a given unit, as well as an estimate of resources necessary to carry out the programme and the revenues needed to cover those expenditures. Budget can be classified as vertical or horizontal budget. A vertical budget includes the various income and expenditure estimates (by. line item function, object, and cost centre) in a given fiscal year while a horizontal budget will include current estimates for a given fiscal year, compared to prior audited income and expenditure and projection of costs into the future. Hence, the budget is-statement of purpose and review of income and expenditures by function to lain past, current and future financial practice

Purpose of budgeting

The purposes of "budgeting which can be attributed to the financial techniques control in the school system are to:

- help in allocating scarce resources
- serve as an instrument for achieving both internal and external accountability.
- influence economic condition of the education sector.

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- translate plans into action.
- provide legal basis for spending and accountability.
- facilitate the continuous monitoring, evaluation, and control of financial resources of the school.
- assist better integration and coordination of school activities.
- serve as analytical tool. To shape the future.

With computers, internet accessibility, and growing public interest, one can assume that school budgeting, accounting and auditing procedures will become more systematic, accessible and transparent to stakeholders of education nation-wide.

Planning School Budget

Budget planning refers to a process of preparing set of decision for action in future (Oyedeji, 1996). Statement of Budget planning strategies include the need to source information about the educational programme and estimate of resource revenue in past years, present and future, needs from those concerned in the budget necessary to cover those expenditures determine,, for example head of Departments, members of board of governors etc, Knowledge based upon such available information will, help the school administrations to formulate the draft budget to be put- before his board. The cost of each educational plan is reviewed in terms of available resources, to determine those to be discarded or to be added.

In the school system like a formal organization, budget can be presented like a balance sheet. The budget became deficit if expenditure is greater than revenue while recurrent revenue is the money received from year to year by way of fees and. other charges, and recurrent expenditure s expenditure on running cost such as equipment materials and others (Ajia, 2002).

Budgeting Procedure

According to Ogundele (2013) cooper suggested a procedure for budgeting in the school system. According to him, budget must be related to existing and' prospective patterns of organizational responsibility and to the hierarchy of policy decisions, it must reflect and serve internal organizational purpose; it is an expression of proposed executive policy which may be modified by the legislative body (the school board of governors and ministry of education) on adoption, it becomes work plan for that budgetary decisions are actually- implemented. Budget administration affects the efficient use of resources by ensuring the monies are spent as planned.

Consequently, for improving resources utilization it must rest largely on efforts, to improve the methods of formulating school budget Olusoji (2010).

School budget formulation means developing a plan for acquiring and allocating school financial resources. This plan is summarized in the school budget, which must then be approved by the Ministry of Education/ Board of Governor in accordance with the sated standard. It is important to recognize the political nature of school budgeting and design to fairly represent those with an interest education including citizens; administrators, teachers, parents, and students.

In an ideal secondary school situation the key actors in-the ' budgeting process in the school system include the principal, Head of Departments. School Bursa- or Finance Clerk, - P.T.A representatives and any other appointed members of staff of the school.

There is need to briefly discuss the school budget cycle. The preparatory work for the school budget is usually Commenced a month before the beginning of the new academic year at the H.O.S's level, preliminary estimates of their departmental needs for the year or term as the case may be and submitted to the budget committee. At the same time, the management. Finance Clerk and members of the budget committee prepare tentative budget guidelines.

Jennifer (2010) noted that the budget committee discusses the proposed figures with the school head, which also have information available about general economic conditions of the school. The school head, then established budget guidelines in conformity with his general plans for schools activities.

The budget committee then requests formal detailed estimates from all departments in conformity with the budget committee. The budget document itself is then prepared and-in. early first week of the new academic year is presented by the school administrator to the board of governors meeting for-first approval.

Budgeting practices

Budgeting practices can be divided in to two namely traditional and modern budgeting practices. The tradition practice is line-item budgeting and the modern practices include zero based budgeting SBB, functional budgeting planning-programming system budgeting practice and others. The traditional budgetary process begins with an enrolment and revenues for the budgeted year. Enrolments are relatively easy to predict by just adding new entrants to those who remain in the system to produce a fairly

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accurate prediction of enrolment to determine the amount" of money it receives from State and in some States in Nigeria, the amount is legally permitted to raise locally.

Once the enrolment and revenue projections are made, department heads and school head are usually asked to submit budget requests according to their particular needs.

Line Item Budgeting

A line-item account is usually use by each school, with a number of expenditure categories (e.g instructional supplies," textbooks, supplementary books, transportation, health-supplies, and telephone and office supplies). The most widely used classification accounts is line item. It may be very short or consist of hundreds of separate entries. The primary purpose of line-item budgets is accurate control over such expenditures. The obvious disadvantage of such a budget is that it reduces an administrator's ability to respond to a new situation or to divert funds' where they are most needed in addition to the fact that is virtually useless for planning and management since the functions of the expenditures are not explained and the particular need are lost in spending aggregated by line (Durosaro, 2000).

Another classification scheme is called a functional budget. A' functional budget reports data on expenditures in terms of the major purpose for which they are function. Budgeting is used by most government owned schools since it organizes spending around the basic functions of the system, such as instrument, student support, operations, administration, and transportation. In addition, functions are sub-divided, while the objects being purchased are also specified. Dersonne service or salaries and' benefits may be handled function support, or plant maintenance. Its advantage is that it is understandable to the public and it enables citizens compare the use of funds in one school to another (Gale Encyclopedia of Education).

Zero-Based Budgeting

ZBB began with the assumption that the school system starts out yearly with a clean state. Thus each function programme and has to justify its expenditures annually, relating all to school goals and objectives avoiding habitual spending. The disadvantage of ZBB is that it is more of exercise than a practical reality due to the fact that it does not take care of many costs that are fixed across annual budgets, and activities are force comparison of and choices among programmes and activities are often difficult to compare adequate.

Each decision package must be justified on the bases of cost analysis. There are main features of zero based budgets, and they are briefly identified as follows:

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1. Activities of every department are divided into decision-package and each providing information.
2. Each decision package is evaluated and ranked in the order of decreasing importance.
3. Resources are allocated according to the final rank by the management. Decision to allocate resources to priority items would be made rather quickly Ogundele (2012)

Programme-Planning Budgeting

Programme-Planning-Budgeting System (PPBS) rarely used in education, PPBS would require school to spell out their mission; and goals, lay out alternatives to reach these goals and objectives, attribute costs to each choice, analyse the costs, select the best option, build the budget around this outcome, and finally feed data back to adjust the costs to the results while this so complex, and the programmes so numerous that school and possibly, the government cannot readily sustain this technique Durosaro (2000).

The programme approach stresses the end product, such as providing a retaliatory striking force of a certain magnitude, relative to the goals of organization as such activities, rather than the input of various types of materials and manpower. Secondly, programme budgeting stresses the relationship between programmes and the inputs necessary to produce them. Programme here include all work seeking attain in the same objectives.

Ogundele (2001) explained that the output budgeting and other accounting-based school management techniques require many arbitrary decisions to be taken on the nature of school production process. For example, it is fundamental to the philosophy and practice of P.P.B.S that information should be collected and classified on a programme or objective-related basis. Thus costs are not classified by functional expenditures (expenditures on academic staff, and on materials) but by programme requirements (cost of academic staff required for teaching programme etc).

The major strength of the programme budget is that it provides a more useful basis for evaluation of requests by department; and the budgeting committee by concentrating on end product instead of inputs by providing better information on the cost and benefit.

Programming involves the statement of the relationship of inputs and outputs under various alternatives, to accomplish the desire objectives. Planning is extended forward

for several years, rather than focusing attention on the current year, P.P.B.S seeks to consider overall programmes in light of objective.

School-Site Based Budgeting

SBB is concerned with who will do the budgeting and where in the school hierarchy the decisions will be made. In attempts to bring the budgeting process closer to end-users- the teachers, parents, and school administrators- SBB encourages, if not requires, decision-making which community examine their programmes and to set their budgets to meet their particular needs as part of the process of shared decision-making. Under SBB, community must determine who will serve in SBB committees; which decisions and resources are devoted to schools and using what formulas; how much autonomy is granted to spend for local needs, how to analyse the budgets at each school-and what training and support are needed to make SBB work effectively.

In practice, school or ministry or boards thereof will utilize variations of many, if not all, of the above methods in compiling their budgets. For example, a school administrator may require teachers to justify their budget request in the development of a school (SBB) budget.

Accounting

The huge investments that are made in the educational sector made it prone to fraudulent activities and asset misappropriation. These assets can however be safeguarded by having and running formidable accounting system that will significantly strengthen the internal control of a school. School administrator will be careful while handing school's property because they know that this is a system in place that watches and monitors them.

Keeping proper accounting records in school system is an indispensable tool to ensure there is no embezzlement of any kind by responsible officers of the school and to enhance sweet experience of learning by the students (Chinweike, 2014).

Generally, school budget is a reflection of its educational mission, goals and philosophies: than the accounting system becomes the method by which a State or Nation can assess the overall effectiveness of the financial plan of education. In fact the accounting structure (line items spending categories, costing and spending procedures) is reflected in the budget, and will later be used in auditing the system for legal appropriate, and responsible spending.

Accounting system as an art of recording, summarizing reporting and analyzing financial transactions can be a simple, utilitarian check register or as whi Microsoft Office Accounting, it can be a complete record of all the activities of a business, providing details of every aspect of the business, allowing the analysis of business trends, and providing insight- into future prospects. (Nwachuwuwn 2014).

The justification for the use of accounting in school system include to allow the community or the state to assess whether it has the financial resources to meet the needs of its programmes to set up a procedure by which all fiscal activities in a school can be accumulated, categorized, reported, and controlled/ Accounting provides the budget with the information necessary for a/horizontal comparison (previous year, current year, and future annual revenues) of actual vertical (line-item) expenditures and budget performance; provides proper fiscal controls and accountability, which in turn, build public trust and confidence in the education.

Auditing

Importance of auditing in school system cannot be overemphasized hence they in hence they including help to ensure a prudent use of taxpayer money, provide a sound internal control structure and safeguard government or private owners assets, for the benefit of our children and communities.

Schools raising and spending of money must be reviewed' and audited on the yearly basis or as needed or determined by the governing body. In addition, an effective management system would include internal reviews and audits on a continuous basis to ensure accuracy and prevent fraud. Thus, two broad categories of audit-internal and external are important in holding school accountable for the use of public funds.

There are four factors that need to be considered by a board of education when selecting an auditor, or an audit committee members or hiring an auditor, be it internal or external auditor the Another type of audit is a performance audit, which focuses on economy and efficiency of the Education Authority or Teaching Service Commission by examining their controls for weaknesses, which would expose possible mismanagement or fraud or misappropriation as the case may be.

Conclusion

The need for budgeting accounting and auditing school system are inevitable. These strategies attempt to determine the effective and efficient uses of resources school

management can structure, organize and operationalize the financial plan (the budget), provides the road map by which trustees and" board of education members, and state government official plan (the budget), provides the roadmap by which trustees and board of education members, and state government officials can evaluate schools financial status; it provides the necessary procedures-and data to enable an independent certified public accountant to conduct schools annual financial audit; and to support the operation. When a school budget is aligned to the needs and programmes of school and nation; when the accounting structure is clear and well-constructed to reflect the way money is collected and spent, review and audit as needed, then the fund can be described as effectively, efficiently, and productively used.

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